

THE THOUGHT OF DEATH LINGO-CULTURAL OPTIONS

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Abstract Death is associate degree present development thus it's been recognized in human cultures and languages the globe over. For this reason it are often explained in terms of linguistics primes representing the core of the meaning, regardless of the language a given folks is aware of and uses. Death appears to possess occupied a big position in numerous cultures, that is mirrored by an over plus of rituals and rites dedicated to it and discovered across completely different ethnic communities.

Key words: cognitive model, linguistic worldview, frame, death.

Аннотация Смерть — это современное развитие, поэтому она была признана в человеческих культурах и языках по всему миру. По этой причине это часто объясняется с точки зрения лингвистических простых чисел, представляющих ядро значения, независимо от языка, который знает и использует данный народ. Смерть, по-видимому, занимала важное место во многих культурах, что отражается в большом количестве ритуалов и обрядов, посвященных ей и обнаруженных в самых разных этнических сообществах.

Ключевые слова: когнитивная модель, языковая картина мира, фрейм, смерть.

The concept of death, further because the processes of dying are coped with and delineate by, among others, such skilled teams as physicians, philosophers, non-secular leaders, poets, writers, however as a phenomenon it may be subject to

linguistic analysis each in terms of the lexical exponents used in language further because the psychological feature constructs that it'd be a focal element. The try are going to be created within the following discussion to stipulate the weather of the frame of death, seen from the angle of the ecru tradition. Moreover, the archetypical association of death, i.e. for natural causes and not self-inflicted or conditioned by third parties, will be exemplified. It is necessary to notice that specific varieties or causes of death, comparable to suicide, murder, mercy killing, etc., shall not be taken into thought for the actual fact that they're not treated as prototypical. It's additionally necessary to focus on that on various occasions euphemisms are used in situ of these vocabulary items that directly address the thought of death and connected phenomena. Once the service is over, the coffin is allotted of the church / chapel / funeral parlor and brought to the topographic point during a ceremonial occasion procession. The coffin is carried out by pallbearers – people "helping automobile to hold or formally escorting the coffin at a funeral", members of the family or friends – and sometimes placed {in adoring in associate degree exceedingly in a very} hearse, i.e. "a carriage or car created for carrying a coffin at a funeral", that takes it to the grave. The coffin is down into the grave and coated by a grave-cover ("a stone block covering a grave"). Just in case the ashes are placed in an urn, it's either buried within the grave or placed in a niche in a columbarium, i.e. "a subterranean sepulcher, having in its walls niches or holes for niche urns; additionally one of these niches or recesses". once a loved one dies, the remaining members of the family are in mourning. Mourning is mostly thought-about as "grieving caused by the death of a person". it's "the action of feeling or expressing sorrow for the death of a person; sorrow or grief for a deceased person; associate degree instance of this; an expression of grief or lament for a deceased person". However, it additionally refers to "the typical or ceremonial manifestation of sorrow for the death of a person; esp. the carrying of garments related to death (in Western society usually black). Such a perspective is not possible in Western tradition, wherever the deceased are revered and their remains are either buried whole or

cremated. Different mortuary rites, which can be shocking for non-residents are discovered in Borneo and elsewhere. In keeping with Metcalf (2006: 176), they last for extended periods of time, "for months or maybe years, and involve moving corpses from an area of temporary storage to a final grand mausoleum". Variations are often noted for numerous cultures and, what's closely connected with them, numerous language communities. pertaining to the Yankee ways that of responding to death Thorsby (2006: 1) points out that the Yankee character usually adapts recent {ways that ways in that} to new, and also the United States, a fancy civilization created from its own autochthonic folks and multitude of cultures from round the world, has reinvented the response to death. Instead of an area of your time with stress on separation, death and the ceremony rituals encompassing it became an area for renewal and reaffirmed connectedness between family and friends of the deceased. a special approach is experienced by Aboriginal peoples of Australia. The approach a body is treated and disposed of reflects the "Aboriginal read of death as a transition through which a person moves to a different part of existence" (Venbrux & Tonnaer 2009: 88). The spirit of the late relative or community member has to be hunted person far away from the globe of the living to the world of the dead, which could entail partial or thorough destruction of not solely the deceased person' remains however additionally his / her material goods. Considering the above, in a top level view of the script of seen from numerous cultural perspectives, numerous components would be gift and just some would be overlapping. These embrace ceremony rites and bound procedures that are irreversibly connected with the passage from the globe of the living to the world of the dead. For instance, in Western tradition itself, either the body would be placed during a coffin or casket, or the remains would be placed in an urn. Those containers, in turn, would be placed within the ground, i.e. buried correct or, just in case of the urn; it'd even be placed in a columbarium. Such components would be absent if the script were to be drawn for Yankee Indian tribes (see Cox 2003), Hindus (see Rambachan 2003), or Aborigines. Ceremony traditions cultivated in Japan (see Suzuki 2003) or China (see

Crowder 2003) also is quite advanced and entails numerous activities and practices. The script would assume a special type and embrace still different components for Jews (see Schindler 2003) or Muslims (see Grand Turk 2003). In Muslim tradition, a coffin isn't used for burial. Grand Turk (ibid. 651-652) states that the body is wrapped during a shroud and placed directly in a 4 to 6-feet deep grave within the position facing Mecca. Just in case of some cultures or communities it's troublesome to speak of the hiding practices at all, as corpses will be preserved. Bolt (2009: 110) notes such types of body disposition as embalming and mummification, body donation to science, preservation (it could be a technique of preservation, that "consists of replacement the natural body fluids with a plastic to preserve the tissues, which makes it potential to show the body in any desired position"), cryonics, and mortuary cannibalism. Burial perplexed is another risk of doing away with the dead body. However, attitudes towards this kind of body removal vary cross-culturally. Steward (2009: 123) highlights the actual fact that some cultures read water because the correct place for the dead, whereas others see it solely as an area of expedient or because the place to eliminate criminals or different social outcasts. The previous perspective is maybe best exemplified by the Hindu belief that the stream Ganges could be a sacred place which will take the dead to heaven. Also, the distinction between ground burial and burial perplexed is that by being placed in water the body isn't buried as such. throughout "a ritual of separation during which the deceased is symbolically aloof from the globe of the living and placed within the realm of the dead" (ibid.: 124), performed in case of land burial, the body is positioned within a grave within the ground, and also the soil placed over it constitutes not solely a symbolic however also a true barrier between the 2 worlds, those of the living and the dead. Multiple variations are often illustrated for traditions practiced by communities the globe over. Diversity is additionally noted in the approach prayers are same and mourning is observed. Positioning the body in the grave or another place of quietus is another space wherever numerous procedures are employed. Hence, it's apparent that one universal script cannot be designed. Nevertheless,

regardless of the range of practices and rituals, all cultures universally pay relation to their ancestors, in one type or another. Another essential distinction between numerous cultural and spiritual teams is that the approach cemeteries are perceived and treated.. Customarily, a headstone referred to as matzeivah, is placed at the pinnacle of the grave as a tribute to the deceased. In contrast to Christian tradition of transportation flowers, pebbles are left on the tombstones as a token of memory. Muslim cemeteries aren't simply known as such, because of the actual fact that they contain few markers across open areas of space. in contrast to Christian cemeteries, in Muslim ones distinguishable grave markers or tombstones aren't generally used. MacLean and Williams (ibid. 170) state that now upon death a two-stage cleansing ritual is performed with quiet reverence of samisen family members. The body is organized during a sleeping position, and then wrapped in cloth, 3 layers for men and 5 layers for girls. There's one exception to the current preparation. Within the case of martyrs [...] the body isn't washed and is buried in the same apparel worn upon death. Even if women are not prohibited from attending a funeral, it's typically a male activity. Women, however, aren't allowable to hold the body or escort it to the gravesite. Such restrictions are not gift in Christian ceremony procedures; therefore Muslin-specific components wouldn't be enclosed during a script characteristic of a special cultural background or a spiritual group. In Mexican cemeteries the joyous rather than excessively solemn character is mirrored within the typical grave decorations together with colourful notes, cards, animated balloons, toys, canned drinks or personal possessions. The crosses also are of times painted or wrapped in bright colors (ibid. 171). Native Yankee funerary rituals are as numerous because the tribes themselves, however, recent traditions are being steady replaced by those influenced by the up to date society and living. Nevertheless, MacLean and Williams (ibid. 172) signifies that "some tribes are proverbial to possess placed their dead on above-ground scaffolds or in trees from that bones were gathered and deposited in earth pits. Some tribes practiced cremation; different buried their dead within the floors of their houses, and a few designed spirit houses." regardless of the

variations in ceremony procedures, most tribes buried valuables in conjunction with dead bodies to confirm "a sleek transition into the spirit world". Comparatively remote tribes tend to continue long practices comparable to covering the graves with ancient social group blankets, wrapping the bodies either with blankets or in special skin robes, inserting prayer ribbons or colorful prayer sticks at the burying ground to alter the late tribe members to enter the spirit world. 6. Conclusions it are often complete from the higher than define of the thought-about frame of death (as well because the respect to the potential frame-related script) that a number of its components are culture-dependent. In fact, they're additionally religion-dependent, as the above delineate sketch refers to European tradition that is definitely distinct from burial rites preserved and observed by members of different non secular communities, regardless of their nationality. the globe over, these rituals are as numerous as starting from terribly solemn to joyous, which might embrace instances of performing arts or other festivities, comparable to, for instance, in Mexican culture. In up to date Taiwan, employment of stripteases is meant to encourage folks to require half during a ceremonial occasion and to supply amusement for guests. Various diversities are often noted not solely with respect to the weather constituting the frame however additionally to its part parts, such as tools employed, practices discovered, and sequences of activities described, for instance, by means of scripts. Obviously, the above-outlined description isn't complete as there can be different components that haven't been thought-about within the discussion. As recognized earlier, a precise perspective has been adopted for the presentation of the analyzed psychological feature construct. However, it's essential to say that specific regional varieties may be found. Polish folks are preponderantly Roman Catholic, nevertheless, in numerous areas of the country specific elements of the ceremony are going to be present, that aren't to be found elsewhere (Podhale – the Tatra Mountains area, Pomerania, Podlasie, etc.). Equally to other cultures, Polish lore abounds in various superstitions and beliefs connected with death that also are wide-ranging in keeping with a region⁶. Constant is true of different nations wherever

regional diversity are often also exhibited by the rituals and observances practiced by their inhabitants. It's to be noted that the language related to the above-outlined frame is extremely productive in terms of generating figurative expressions⁷ and metaphors. They represent and replicate the repertoire of beliefs, traditions, and customs discovered by a given national or, more locally, a regional community further because the worldview expressed by and in their language. Any frame, expressed in any language, as a data structure, represents a abstract system and a worldview adopted by a specific language community. However, at intervals this language community, as illustrated by the above-presented psychological feature construct, variations are going to be apparent if certain variables are at play. Within the case of the mentioned frame of death, non-secular beliefs and practices ought to be considered, because the diversity in religious denominations or cultural backgrounds can lead to the range of frame components. a number of those frame elements will be universal, whereas others will be specific for a collection group. Nevertheless, one issue remains unchanged: nothing is definite however death and taxes.

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